

Conductivity of Mixed Aqueous Electrolytes

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The conductivity of mixed electrolytes is never strictly additive. The deviations from ideal behaviour have been reported¹⁻³ in the simple systems like HCl-NaCl and KCl-NaCl. Eventhough these systems have been studied at various concentrations, precise conductivity data is available only for 3-4 compositions at 0.1M. The present work was undertaken to study the behaviour of these simple mixtures covering a large number of compositions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Using AR grade chemicals, solutions of individual electrolytes and their mixtures of 0.1 molarity were prepared in double distilled water. The systems HCl-NaCl, Pb(NO₃)₂-KNO₃ (fig. 1) and BaCl₂-KCl, KCl-NaCl (fig. 2) were studied at 25° and 35° respectively ($\pm 0.01^\circ$). Resistances were measured with an accuracy of ± 0.01 ohm. Jone's type conductivity cell has a cell constant of 3.0612.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The equivalent conductivities of the mixtures were plotted as a function of mol fraction of the first component in the particular system (f_1). The calculated conductivities of the mixtures (by additivity law) are shown by the straight line. The difference between the calculated and observed conductivity ($\Delta\lambda$) is considered as positive when the calculated value is greater than the observed, and negative when it is less than the observed value (I). In the system of HCl-NaCl, $\Delta\lambda$ values are positive from 0.15 to 0.8 and negative from 0.83 to

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0.86 f_1 . The observed deviations are ~ 2.0 units from 0.25 to 0.66 f_1 and ~ 0.8 unit from 0.83 to 0.86 f_1 , which can be ascribed to changes in hydration. Data for the system HCl-KCl at 0.1M and 25° show that $\Delta\lambda$ values are positive, the deviations being 1.65, 2.02 and 1.37 units at 0.25, 0.5 and 0.75 f_1 respectively³. This shows that both the systems behave in a similar fashion over this range.

(II) In the system of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ - KNO_3 , $\Delta\lambda$ values are positive. The maximum deviation observed was 5.7 units at 0.5 f_1 . The large decrease in conductance suggests the formation of PbNO_3^+ ion-pairs (pK dissociation of $\text{PbNO}_3^+ = 1.18$ and $\text{KNO}_3 = -0.2$)⁴, contrary to the three complexes reported by Nayar and Pande⁵. Probably such complexes may not exist at low concentrations (0.1M).

(III) Further, in the system of BaCl_2 -KCl, the maximum deviation is ~ 9.0 conductance units at 0.18 f_1 . The considerable decrease in the observed conductance supports the formation of BaCl^+ ion pairs contrary to the seven complexes reported in the literature⁶⁻⁷. However the break in the curve at 0.2 f_1 supports the formation of the complex $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{KCl}$.

(IV) Finally in the system of KCl-NaCl it is observed that from 0 to 0.65 and 0.9 to 1.0 f_1 , the system behaves ideally whereas from 0.65 to 0.9 f_1 , $\Delta\lambda$ values are positive. The deviations are 0.6, 0.8, 0.8 and 0.4 units at 0.7, 0.75, 0.8 and 0.85 f_1 respectively which may be due to changes in hydration. For this system at 0.1M and 25° Shedlovsky *et al.*¹ have reported the deviations of ~ 0.1 units.

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